

Design and Analysis of Digital Photonic Full Adder

Hamish Ricky M*, Karthic Vijay B, Madhu Rishwanth K

Electronics & Communication Engineering,

School of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, SASTRA Deemed University,
Thanjavur-613401, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract—In this article a photonic full adder (PFA) is implemented using two different photonic devices namely Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) and Directional coupler (DC). The proposed approach is useful for implementing digital photonic circuits and related applications. The detuning phase and coupling coefficients are utilized respectively in MZI and DC for reconfiguration of different digital functionality. and The PFA is modeled using 2D finite element beam propagation method (FE-BPM) method. Finally, a compact numerical model (CNM) is developed and verified using MATLAB to check its suitability.

Index Terms—photonic full adder, digital photonics, arithmetic circuits, photonic gates

I. Introduction

Reconfigurable or programmable systems are configured with soft hardware that can be altered to suit the purpose of the user. Reconfigurability is common in electronic circuits and components with Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) being the best known examples [1]. Programmable Integrated Photonics (PIP) aims at constructing systems on integrated optic chips from the former generic advantages. This includes Field Programmable Photonic Arrays (FPPA) playing a similar role as FPGA in Photonics. While the architecture principle of FPGA and FPPA carry similar features, the operational features are different as FPPAs do not carry digital logic operations. But they can perform a high-speed analog operations acting over the amplitude and phase of the optical signals in a controlled environment.

In this work, the capability of Field Programmable Photonic Array is recognized by building an array using basic photonic elements such as Mach-Zehnder Interferometer (MZI), directional coupler and other required elements. The example circuit for proving the purpose of the simulation was a Full adder circuit made from the recognition of logic gates such as AND, OR, XOR [2-6]. The functionality of these gates are made by altering the phase shift for the Mach-Zehnder Interferometer (MZI) in the first method and finding the phase shift values for the respective gates. In the other method where directional couplers are used, the value of the coupling co-efficient is altered to perform the required gate functionality. Using the phase values and coupling co-efficient values the block element for the respective gates are built and using these blocks any circuit can be made as an array according to the arrangement of the gates specified [7-10].

II. Photonic Components

Programmable multifunctional photonics can implement many functions using suitable programming. Several authors have laid theoretical works on different configurations and programmable logics. They offer versatile solutions for the execution of complex or simple circuits. In electronics, this idea is used by Field Programmable Gate Array. Following a similar principle we propose the execution of an identical concept based on integrated photonics [10-12]. Typical field programmable photonic array is described in Fig.1. The element which we call Field Programmable Photonic Array can implement one or many simultaneous optical circuits using programmable photonic blocks[12-17].

Fig. 1. Programmable Photonic Analog Blocks arranged to form an FPPA [1].

In the existing work, a reconfigurable photonic logic gate was designed using 2×2 Mach-Zehnder Interferometer for digital photonic circuit applications. The Fig. 2 shows a 2×2 MZI with two PIN phase shifters in push-pull configuration. The amount of phase shift is given by the two phase shifters present in the upper and lower arm of the waveguide. The net difference between these two angles gives the phase difference that decides the light intensity equivalent to digital values present in the output port. Using Mach-Zehnder Interferometer, a Mach-Zehnder Modulator is built for performing the logic functions by configuring the phase angles according to the requirement. By checking the output power of the gate from the required gates, the phase angle can be configured. Considering this as a building block, an array of elements can be arranged according to the flow required.

*Corresponding author: hamishrickymars@gmail.com

The different colored element shows a single block element and by altering the phase angle in Mach-Zehnder Interferometer controlling the flow of circuit as required. The existing work uses phase shifter as a main element to cause angle variation to direct the source to required direction. Since the phase of the signal is a very sensitive and has a easily disruptable characteristic, many outside interruptions can cause the result from being accurate and this can be a big hurdle in getting an efficient and trustable output. A small change in the phase angle can cause a big change in the output. Hence, phase angle cannot be a totally reliable characteristic. The interruption can be from anywhere. It can be from another source or due to magnetic interruption or physical disturbances. Another drawback is that, since the MZI has two phase shifters as shown, configuring both the phase shifters is essential. This consumes a lot of time and also a lot of space in the circuit. Considering these drawbacks, an alternate method is presented in this work. The proposed work includes two methods of operation. One includes the existing work based on Mach-Zehnder Interferometer by configuring the phase angles according to the logic gates. And the second method, which overcomes the drawbacks of the existing work using a directional coupler and providing the same function as FPPA by altering the coupling co-efficient.

Fig. 2. Mach-Zehnder Interferometer.

Fig. 3. Directional Coupler.

From the Fig.2, Fig.3 and Fig.4, we can see that the first method has two phase angles to be configured and for the directional coupler just the coupling co-efficient has to be configured. Also it is visible that, Directional

Fig. 4. Configuration of phase shifter and directional coupler available in INTERCONNECT.

coupler circuit occupies much lesser space than the Phase shifter circuit. The work includes, forming the circuit for the individual logic gates and forming an array with these circuits to form a logic, full adder circuit in our case.

III. Digital Photonics

The proposed building block design will act as the building block of the array. A number of said building blocks can be connected and configured accordingly to perform logic functions. A common continuous wave (CW) laser provides the optical input signal to each photonic component, which are configured by their respective control signals to provide the output signal. Each photonic device performs the function of one logic gate and the whole array performs the function of a logic equation. The photodetectors are responsible for converting the optical signals to electrical signals. All the electrical signals are controlled by the programmable switching control. The electronic full adder is shown in Fig.5.

Fig. 5. Digital electronic full adder.

A. Reconfigurable Photonic Full Adder

The systematic arrangement of either MZI or DC is configured to perform full adder functionality. A logical full adder consists of 5 logic gates in total – 2 XOR, 2 AND and 1 OR gates. Therefore, the array was constructed using 5 photonic components and each photonic component was reconfigured to act as the respective logic gate as shown in Fig.6. Different phase shifter values are used to configure MZI as photonic full adder as shown in Table.1.

The circuit was designed in Lumerical INTERCONNECT using both approaches. The appropriate circuit elements were connected according to the circuit diagrams and configured accordingly. The CW laser is connected to

Fig. 6. Reconfigurable photonic full adder using MZI configuration.

Fig. 7. Reconfigurable photonic full adder using DC configuration.

TABLE I

Input configuration of MZI based implementation of full adder.

S1		S2		S3		Sout		Cout	
XOR		AND		AND		XOR		OR	
θ_1	θ_2								
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	300	0	0	180	0	0
0	180	0	60	300	0	180	0	0	0
0	180	0	60	300	60	180	180	0	120
180	0	300	0	300	0	180	0	0	0
180	0	300	0	300	60	180	180	0	120
180	180	300	60	0	0	0	0	240	0
180	180	300	60	0	60	0	180	240	0

a splitter, which splits the optical signal in an even ratio. The 5 output arms of the splitter are connected to 5 UPGs (building blocks) which are logic gates. These building blocks are reconfigured to their respective functionality. The obtained light intensity results are tabulated in Table.2.

The photonic full adder using DC is shown in Fig.7 and the required coupling coefficients are listed in Table.3. The light intensity results are obtained in Table.4.

Based on the photonic full adder results, both MZI and DC based photonic full adder realizations provides the

TABLE II

Results obtained from MZI based photonic full adder.

Input Power = 1 dB				
Power Level (<-0.25 : Logic Low, 0.25 : Logic High)				
S1	S2	S3	Sout	Cout
-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-5	1	-
1	-5	-5	1	-
1	-5	-0.25	-	-0.25
1	-5	-5	1	-
1	-0.25	-	-	-0.25
-	-0.25	-	-	-0.25
-	-0.25	-5	1	-0.25

TABLE III

Coupling coefficient configuration for DC based full adder.

S1	S2	S3	Sout	Cout
XOR	AND	AND	XOR	OR
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0.25	1	0
1	0.25	0.25	1	0
1	0.25	0.75	0	0.75
1	0.25	0.25	1	0
1	0.75	0	0	0.75
0	0.75	0	0	0.75
0	0.75	0.25	0	0.75

same results. But, the complexity associated with MZI is more than DC. The reason why DC is preferred over MZI is that, DC occupies less area when compared with MZI, MZI switch is based on phase variation hence this leads to many unwanted interference causing deflection in angle variation thereby affecting the results. Hence the transmission loss ratio is very much less when compared with MZI switches.

TABLE IV

Results obtained from DC based photonic full adder.

Input Power = 1 dB				
Power Level (<-0.25 : Logic Low, 0.25 : Logic High)				
S1	S2	S3	Sout	Cout
-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-5	1	-
1	-5	-5	1	-
1	-5	-0.25	-	-0.25
1	-5	-5	1	-
1	-0.25	-	-	-0.25
-	-0.25	-	-	-0.25
-	-0.25	-5	1	-0.25

IV. Conclusion

In this work, digital photonic gates, based on Directional Coupler (DC) and Mach-Zehnder Interferometer (MZI) are proposed to perform logical operations, and can be used to form photonic logic block (PLB) similar to programmable logic array (PLA). The PLBs can be configured to perform any logical operations, which incorporate photodiodes and array of UPGs. In this work we used the photonic components to perform the digital operations such as AND, NAND, OR, NOR, XOR, and XNOR. In the MZI based UPGs, the logical operations were performed based on the phase-shift, created by the external electric field. In DC based realizations, the intended operations were carried out using the power coupling mechanism between the adjacent waveguides with the help of external electric field. We performed the comparative study of photonic full adder using MZI and DC based realizations. The larger footprint/layout of the MZI based realization makes them not suitable for the photonic integrated circuit (PIC) applications. The smaller footprint of the DC based realizations enables denser integration of photonic components in the photonic IC applications.

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